

FISP-ProCOP survey -- Security and privacy management in smart systems

* Indicates required question

Who should participate?

The focus of the study is on the organisations from any sector that develop solutions/systems/devices for smart systems. By "*a smart system*" in this survey we mean a system of systems (SoS), an intelligent infrastructure system, cyber-physical system or any other socio-technical system composed of multiple stand-alone integrated information systems that allow delivering a smart solution to the system end users thanks to a collaborative data exchange between systems and organisations.

The survey participant should have a good understanding of the IT system stack and be aware of internal (organisational) realities.

The survey takes about 20 minutes to complete.

What is a Smart System?

A smart system **connects previously separate systems** and **organisations** to deliver better services or products. Smart systems are designed to improve efficiency, enhance decision-making, and **create new value** by connecting different systems and organisations.

Examples:

- **Smart Factory:** In a smart factory, machines, robots, and supply chains are connected. This allows for automated production, predictive maintenance, and optimised resource allocation.
- **Smart Logistics and Supply Chain:** Using sensors, GPS tracking, and data analytics to optimize delivery routes, track shipments in real-time, and manage warehouse operations more efficiently.
- **Smart city:** Traffic lights, public transportation, and emergency services are all separate systems, but a smart city integrates them so that, for example, traffic lights adjust automatically based on real-time traffic flow, or emergency services are dispatched more efficiently based on sensor data.
- **Smart healthcare:** Smart healthcare systems connect hospitals, doctors, and patients. This can enable remote monitoring, personalized treatment plans, and faster access to medical records.

What is NOT a smart system:

- any standalone system with AI-based features
- a standalone system
- a set of isolated technologically advanced systems

1. By using this template, you understand the usage tool developed by CHESS academic partners. If the results of this questionnaire or the FISP-ProCOP answers analyser are published, I promise to acknowledge CHESS project. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes, I agree

Contact information

2. **Your name**

3. **Contact e-mail**

4. **What is the name of your organisation?**

5. **Which sector does your organisation belong to?**

Mark only one oval.

- Information Technology and Communication (ITC)
- Banking and Financial Services
- Transportation and Logistics
- Healthcare and Pharmaceuticals
- Manufacturing
- Retail and E-commerce
- Education and Research
- Government and Public Sector
- Other: _____

6. **What is your position/role in the organisation?**

Mark only one oval.

- Information security officer
- CTO
- Product owner/manager/analyst
- System analyst
- Process owner/manager/analyst
- Project manager
- Software architect
- Security architect/engineer
- CEO
- IT manager
- Other: _____

Section "Organisation"

The following questions are related to the *organisation's design and strategy*.

The questions aim to define how the organisation's strategy guides the processes based on the strategic objectives, how the organisational design and strategy itself are guided by the external factors (e.g., legal and regulatory provisions), how the organisation's structure peoples by the established culture towards information security, and how the organisation's strategy drives the architecture of the technical security measures.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

7. **1.1. What is the main objective of your smart system?**

8. **1.2. How many active end-users does your smart system have?**

Mark only one oval.

- Up to 1,000
- 1,001 – 10,000
- 10,001 – 100,000
- 100,001 – 1,000,000
- More than 1,000,000
- I don't know

9. **1.3. How much is your company involved in the lifecycle of your smart system?**

Mark only one oval.

- We use the ready-to-use solution which is not under development
- We use the ready-to-use solution which is continuously updated by the system provider
- We use services of the outsourcing company(s) who manages the system we use
- We use services of the outsourcing company(s) who continuously updates the system based on our needs
- There is a small development/support team who manage the system in-house which was developed by external service provider
- We have a development team that is fully responsible for the system, its support and development
- I don't know

10. **1.4. With how many external systems is your system integrated?**

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- 1-2
- 3-4
- 5+
- I don't know

11. **1.5. What are the challenges your company faces during the usage/development/support of your smart system?**

Section "Actors"

The following questions are related to the *actors* relevant for your smart system.

The questions aim to define the stakeholders (including physical and legal entities, internal and external) that have an interest or are involved in the smart system lifecycle (design, developments, support, or usage)

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

12. **2.1. Who are the users of your products/services of the smart system?**

If there are multiple users, separate them with "," (comma)

13. **2.2. Who are the service providers for your products/services in the smart system?**

If there are multiple service providers, separate them with "," (comma)

14. **2.3. Who are the other stakeholders for your products/services in the smart system?**

If there are multiple stakeholders (including partners, data users, processors, IaaS and SaaS providers, etc. from both public and private sectors), separate them with "," (comma)

15. **2.4. What are the roles/goals of the mentioned users, service providers, and stakeholders?**

16. **2.5. How the mentioned users, service providers, and stakeholders are related to one another (e.g., dependent for some services)?**

Section "Information"

The following questions are related to the *information* manipulated within for your smart system.

17. **2.6.1.1. What kind of information (or data objects) is used within your smart system?**

Specify one type of personally identifiable information (PII) or non-PII information used in your system

18. **2.6.1.2. How the information (or data object) mentioned in the previous question is used within a smart system?**

Describe in which services and/or processes the mentioned information is used and how (stored/shared/processed).

19. **2.6.1.3. What are the security criteria for the information (or data objects) in the previous question?** *

Check all that apply.

- Confidentiality
 Integrity
 Availability
 Other: _____

20. **2.6.1.4. Can the specified information be characterised as Personally identifiable information (PII)?** *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes *Skip to question 21*
 No *Skip to question 24*

Personally identifiable information (PII): 1

21. **2.6.1.5. Who is the Controller of this data with respect to GDPR?**

22. **2.6.1.6. Who is (are) the Processor(s) of this data with respect to GDPR?**

23. **2.6.1.7. Who this data can be shared with?**

Information objects

24. **Is any other information (or data objects) is used within your smart system? ***

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No *Skip to question 32*

Information objects: 2

25. **2.6.2.1. What kind of information (or data objects) is used within your smart system?**

Mention Personally identifiable information (PII) or non-PII information

26. **2.6.2.2. How the information (or data object) in the previous question is used within a smart system?**

Describe in which services and/or processes the mentioned information is used and how (stored/shared/processed).

27. **2.6.2.3. What are the security criteria for the information (or data objects) in the previous question? ***

Check all that apply.

Confidentiality

Integrity

Availability

Other: _____

28. **2.6.2.4. Can the specified information be characterised as Personally identifiable information (PII)?**

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No *Skip to question 32*

Personally identifiable information (PII): 2

29. **2.6.2.5. Who is the Controller of this data with respect to GDR?**

30. **2.6.2.6. Who is (are) the Processor(s) of this data with respect to GDPR?**

31. **2.6.2.7. Who this data can be shared with?**

Section "Organisational Constraints"

The following questions are related to the *organisational constraints*. This category refers to the factors that affect the system and are set up by the external entities – through (i) legislation and regulations and (ii) standards.

32. **3.1. Which security or privacy-related legislation and/or regulations affect your smart system?** *

Select all that apply. If there are multiple regulations you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR)
- European Union directive 2010/40/EU (7 July 2010) (a.k.a. ITS Directive)
- Consumer protection directives 2019/770 and 2019/771
- UNECE regulation No 155 Cyber security and cyber security management system (from 2020)
- NIS2 directive
- Cyber Resilience Act
- Not applicable
- Other: _____

33. **3.2. Which cyber/information security standard(s) does your organisation follow?** *

Select all that apply. If there are multiple standards you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- No standards are applicable to our intelligent transportation system
- Estonian Information Security Standard
- Předpis 181/2014 Sb. (zákon o kybernetické bezpečnosti)
- ISO/IEC 27001
- Other standards from ISO/IEC 27000-series
- ETSI standards series (e.g. ETSI TS 102 941, 102 731, 103 097)
- NIST Special Publications (e.g. NIST SP 800-39, NIST SP 800-37)
- ISO/IEC 29001
- Not applicable
- Other: _____

34. **3.3. Is your organisation certified according to the standards you selected in the previous question?** *

If your organisation is certified according to only some of the standards selected in the previous answer, please specify according to which in the "Other..." option.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, we are certified according to all the standards selected in the previous answer
- No, not certified
- Not applicable
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 1"

The following questions are related to the stakeholders of your smart system as well as policies & practices in your organisation.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

35. **4.1. What are the practices and policies used for assuring information security and/or privacy management in your company?** *

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Following the selected risk management framework
- Following the selected (cyber) security framework
- National (cyber) security strategy
- Threat modelling
- Penetration testing
- Security Development Lifecycle
- We don't use any
- Other: _____

36. **4.2. Which security principles are followed for the smart system? ***

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Security by design
- Least privilege
- Least functionality
- Privacy by design
- Data minimisation
- I don't know
- Not applicable
- Other: _____

37. **4.3. Which security and privacy training are established for your system users? ***

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Introducing the privacy policy during the first-time onboarding to the system
- Introducing the information security measure of the system that concerns their data or behaviour
- Regular reminders about privacy policy aspects
- Phishing training
- We don't have any
- Not applicable
- I don't know
- Other: _____

38. **4.4. Which information security and privacy training are established for the employees in your organisation?** *

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Cyber hygiene trainings
- Trainings for raising awareness about security threats
- Data protection trainings
- Phishing training
- Not applicable
- We don't have any
- Other: _____

39. **4.5. How does your organisation store and distribute knowledge about security and privacy management practices?** *

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Organisational manuals and/or guidelines
- System documentation
- The dedicated people controls the unwritten "know-how"
- Unwritten rules followed by the teams
- We don't have any
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 2"

The following questions are related to the technological profile of your organisation.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

40. **5.1. Which of the following architectural measures are used in your smart system?**

*

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Cloud-based system
- Public Key Infrastructure (PKI)
- Identity and Access Management (IAM)
- Zero trust
- Storage of sensitive personal data on the data subject's device
- Securing data in transit
- Multi-party computation (MPC)
- Anonymous authentication
- Blockchain-based system
- Single Sign-On (SSO)
- I don't know
- Other: _____

41. **5.2. Which measure are used for assuring authenticity of the data received from your partners and used in the smart system?**

42. **5.3. Which technologies are used in your smart system for authentication and access control?** *

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with ";" (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Role-based access control
- Anonymous credential system
- Attribute-based credentials and access control
- Multi-factor authentication (MFA)
- RFID authentication
- Biometric-based authentication
- Pseudorandom identity assignment
- We don't have any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

43. **5.4. Which measures are used in your smart system for secure communication between parties?** *

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with ";" (comma)

Check all that apply.

- TLS protocol
- IPSec protocol
- VPN solution
- Custom end-to-end encryption
- Custom asymmetric encryption
- Other secured communication protocol
- Not applicable
- We don't have any
- I don't know
- Other: _____

44. **5.5. Which cryptographic measures are used in your smart system? ***

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- RSA digital signature
- Homomorphic encryption
- Zero-Knowledge Proof
- Oblivious pseudorandom function (OPRF)
- Trusted execution environment (TEE)
- Group signature
- Elliptic curve cryptography
- Diffie-Hellman group key exchange
- Hash-based message authentication codes
- Oblivious transfer protocol
- I don't know
- We don't have any
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: System functionality"

This section contains question about functionality-specific measures in you intelligent infrastructure system.

45. **5.6.1. Do you have payment functionality in your system? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Yes Skip to question 46
- No Skip to question 47

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: Payment"

Measures for protecting payments

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

46. **5.6.2. Which technologies are used in your smart system for payment? ***

Check all that apply.

- Card-based payment
- Token-based payment
- Anonymous payment
- Automated payment using smart contract
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: System functionality"

This section contains question about functionality-specific measures in you smart system.

47. **5.7.1. Do you have functionality of pass/reservation document creation in your smart system? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Yes *Skip to question 48*
- No *Skip to question 49*

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: Pass/reservation document"

Measures for protecting pass/reservation document

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

48. **5.7.2. Which technologies are used in your smart system for pass/reservation document? ***

Check all that apply.

- Blind signature
- Anonymous reservation/ticket
- Presenting proof-of-knowledge
- Other: _____

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 3: Other"

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

49. **5.8. What are the other security- or privacy-preserving technologies used in your intelligent transportation system which was not mentioned?**

50. **5.9. Do you consider employing post-quantum cryptography in the future in your smart system? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, we already employ this
- Yes (within 1 - 3 years)
- Yes (in 3+ years)
- No
- I do not know

51. **5.10. How do you coordinate security and privacy management efforts with your service provider?** *

Check all that apply.

- Joint incident response plan
- Audit of our service providers' security and privacy practices
- Data Processing Agreements (DPAs)
- Reviewing certifications (e.g., ISO 27001, SOC 2) and audit reports of our service providers
- Required periodic security and privacy assessments for our service providers
- Service level agreements (SLAs) that define expectations for security and privacy performance
- Collaboration with service providers on security and privacy risks
- I don't know

Section "Security and Privacy measures. Part 4: Processes"

The following questions are related to processes established for managing your smart system.

The glossary with terms used in this survey can be accessed [here](#).

52. **6.1. Which of the following principles are used during your system development/support?** *

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Privacy-related testing and verification
- Secure programming
- Secure Development Lifecycle
- Security testing
- Outsourced development
- Separation of development, test and production environments
- Change management
- Threat modelling
- I don't know
- Not applicable
- Other: _____

53. **6.2. Which security monitoring measures are used for your smart system? ***

Select all that apply. If there are multiple options you want to add in "Other...", separate them with "," (comma)

Check all that apply.

- Intrusion detection system
- Security incident and event management systems (SIEM)
- Behavioural analytics system
- Network traffic analyser
- Vulnerability scanner
- Not applicable
- I don't know
- We don't have any
- Other: _____

54. **6.3. As a part of which business processes you smart system is used?**

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